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The Use of Teacher-Made Digital Games in Teaching Mathematics 3

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to find out the effectiveness of teacher-made digital games in teaching Mathematics among Grade 3 Learners for the school year 2022-2023. This study used experimental single group post-test and pre-test design. The respondents of this study were the 35 Grade 3 learners in Maitum Elementary School. Total enumeration was applied to get the desired population of the respondents. Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were formulated and established: First, majority of the learners obtained a low pre-test scores before the use of teacher-made digital games. Second, majority of the learners obtained a high post-test score after the use of teacher-made digital games. Lastly, there was a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the learners. Therefore, the use of teacher-made digital games was effective in teaching Mathematics 3. Moreover, incorporating digital games created by teachers into the teaching of Mathematics at the third-grade level can have positive educational implications. These implications could include increased learners' engagement, improved understanding of mathematical concepts, enhanced problem-solving skills, and potentially more enjoyable learning experiences.

Keywords: *educational management, experimental research, teacher-made, digital games, grade 3 learners*

Introduction

Global academic issues include access to quality Digital games have become increasingly popular in teaching due to their ability to engage students and enhance learning outcomes. However, several global issues are also associated with using digital games in education. One of the primary concerns is the potential for addiction and overuse, which can lead to negative impacts on academic performance, physical health, and social relationships. Additionally, there needs to be more regulation and quality control in the digital game industry, which can result in inappropriate content and potentially harmful messaging. There is a need to ensure that digital games are accessible and equitable for all learners, regardless of socio-economic status or access to technology. While digital games have great potential in education, it is essential to address these global issues to ensure their responsible and effective use in the classroom (Asrial et al., 2020; Risdiyanti & Prahmana, 2020).

Moreover, digital games are increasingly recognized as a valuable tool in teaching due to their ability to engage students and enhance learning outcomes. Digital games may foster creativity and teamwork while offering students dynamic and immersive learning opportunities that enhance critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making abilities. Digital games may also be tailored to each student's requirements and interests, making for compelling and entertaining individualized learning experiences. Because of this, digital games have the power to completely transform the way we instruct and learn, improving accessibility, effectiveness, and engagement for learners of all ages and backgrounds (Soboleva et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2018).

Similarly, learning mathematics presents various challenges for many children due to its complex and often tedious nature. Educational video games have the potential to address these challenges and positively impact mathematics learning and attitudes. Video games can consume children's attention for hours, providing instruction and engaging learning experiences. Mathematics affects all aspects of human life. Numbers are fundamental to social, economic, political, geographical, scientific, and technical elements. As well-designed mathematics curricula and educational systems are the cornerstone of scientific, technical, and economic growth, research demonstrates that industrialized nations have greatly profited from them (Hui & Mahmud, 2023).

Today, a global trend in modern mathematics education is the focus on teaching and developing students' computational thinking skills. Formulating and solving a problem in a way that makes use of information processing tools is known as computational thinking. The emergence of information and communication technology impacts every aspect of society. Therefore, to become a contemporary person, one must be willing to investigate the potential of new digital tools. Digital math games have been utilized to support kids' math accomplishments in various domains, such as algebraic problem-solving, strategic thinking, and reasoning. However, studies on digital games that promote them as effective teaching aids indicate that there is still a great deal to learn about how game design elements affect kids' learning. This research project examined how digital math games influenced children's learning (Bertram, 2020; Byun & Joung, 2018).

However, identified Grade 3 learners in Maitum Elementary School often encounter challenges that can hinder their understanding and proficiency in the subject, such as conceptual difficulties. Mathematics concepts can be abstract and complex, requiring students to develop a deep understanding of foundational ideas before progressing to more advanced topics. Difficulties comprehending concepts such as fractions, algebraic equations, or geometric principles can impede students' ability to solve problems and apply mathematical reasoning effectively.

By exploring the effectiveness of teacher-made digital games, this research can contribute valuable insights into the design, implementation, and impact of such games on students' mathematical skills, problem-solving abilities, and overall academic performance. Understanding the benefits and challenges associated with integrating digital games into mathematics education can empower educators to make informed decisions, adapt their instructional strategies, and optimize the learning experience for students, thereby addressing the urgency for research in this area. Hence, this study was conducted to determine the effectiveness of teacher-made digital games in teaching Mathematics among Grade 3 learners.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of teacher-made digital games in teaching Mathematics among Grade 3 Learners for the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, the following objectives were formulated:

1. To determine the pretest-test mean scores of Grade 3 learners in Mathematics.
2. To determine the post-test mean scores of Grade 3 learners in Mathematics.
3. To determine the significant difference between the pretest-test and post-test mean scores of the Grade 3 learners in Mathematics after using teacher-made digital games.

Methodology

This section presents the research design, locale, respondents, sampling procedure, instrumentation, data-gathering procedure employed during the study, and statistical methods used to treat the data gathered.

Research Design

This study used the experimental single-group pretest-test and post-test design. An experimental single-group post-test and pre-test design is a research design used to evaluate the effectiveness of a particular intervention or treatment. In this design, a single group of participants is measured twice, once before the intervention (pretest-test) and once after the intervention (post-test), to assess any changes resulting from the intervention. The main advantage of this design is that it allows researchers to evaluate the effects of an intervention within a single group without the need for a control group (Miller et al., 2020; Rogers & Revesz, 2019).

Little et al. (2020) stated that the one-group pretest-post-test design is without a control group. Moreover, in this design, participants are assessed using a pretest-test to establish a baseline measurement of the variables of interest. Subsequently, the intervention or treatment is administered, and after a certain period, a post-test is conducted to measure any changes in the same variables. Nonetheless, it includes a pretest-test or baseline observation (O1), enabling the researcher to compare the pretest-test and post-test (O2) outcomes to ascertain the treatment's effects. This design addresses history, maturity, testing, instrumentation, statistical regression, and validity. The carefully created supplemental material ascertained the Grade 3 learners' performance level. They completed the pre-test and post-test; they can become more vulnerable to outside effects over time.

The supplementary materials were designed, and media choices were made in the design phase. Supplementary materials were created in the development phase based on choices made in the design phase. The implementation phase included testing additional tools with the target subjects, putting the product in total production, and orienting learners and teachers on using these tools. The evaluation stage included both the formative and summative, providing opportunities for user feedback (Malik & Alam, 2019).

Participants

The respondents of this study were the 35 Grade 3 learners in Maitum Elementary School. Total enumeration was applied to get the desired population of the respondents. Total enumeration refers to collecting data from an entire population or group of interest rather than using a sample or subset for analysis. It involves gathering information from every individual or unit within the defined population, providing a comprehensive and complete dataset for analysis or decision-making (de Assis Lage et al., 2020)

The researcher set the inclusion criteria for selecting the respondents: male or female, regardless of religion and ethnicity, ages 7-9, who were currently enrolled as Grade 3 learners in Maitum Elementary School, Division of Sarangani, for the school year 2022-2023.

On the other hand, specific individuals were excluded from participation in this study, including Grade 3 learners below seven and above nine years old. Additionally, respondents who were unable or unwilling to consent or cooperate in data collection were excluded from the study.

Nevertheless, respondents had the right to withdraw from the study at any stage without providing a reason. Any respondent who chose to withdraw was assured that their decision would not have any negative consequences or impact on their relationship with the school or program. Furthermore, if any respondents displayed discomfort, distress, or emotional unease during the study, appropriate measures were taken to support and ensure their well-being.

Instruments

The instruments used in this study were the Pre-Test, Pre-Test, and Post-test, which the researcher constructed from the supplementary

materials from modules 1 to 4. Each was composed of 30 questions.

Initially, the proponent made a 30-item test instrument based on the second grading lesson. After formulating and completing the draft of the device, the researcher piloted it homogeneously to answer the chosen 30 grade 3 mathematics learners from a neighboring school. After the learners answered the instrument, it was immediately retrieved through the internal consistency method. The method would determine if the examinees passed or failed in item A (1), assigned for a pass or a failure. The process of obtaining a reliability coefficient in this method was determined using Kuder-Richardson Formula 20. Hence,

$$r_{xx} = \left[\frac{N}{N - 1} \right] \left[\frac{SD^2 - \sum p_i q_i}{SD^2} \right]$$

Where N is the number of items, the variance of scores on the test is defined, and the product of the proportion of passed and failed for item i. The symbol pi denotes the proportion of individuals giving item 1 and the proportion failing by, where. The proponent strictly observed the steps in applying the Kuder-Richard Formula 20:

First, the researcher computed the variance of the test scores for the whole group. Second, the researcher determined the proportion of passing each item () and failing each item . Third, the researcher added all the item s by multiplying the and. It provided the worth. Lastly, the computed values were entered into the formula by the researcher. Subsequently, the investigator calculated the data using the computation, which disclosed the reliability of the 30-item test instrument piloted. After learning about the tools ' dependability, the proponent conducted an item analysis to determine each item's index of difficulty and index of discrimination. In order to do this, the researcher meticulously adhered to a few straightforward yet efficient item analysis procedures: In step 1, the test scores were sorted from most significant to lowest. She received one-third of the highest-scoring papers and one-third of the lowest in step 2. The idle one-third was set aside. She tallied the number of pupils in the top and lower groups who selected the alternatives in step 3. She then entered the frequency from Step 3 into Step 4. The proponent calculated the difficulty index in step 5. She employed the following formula: N is the total number of instances in both the higher and lower groups and the sum of the correct answers from the two groups. The percentage of accurate answers for each question is called difficulty. The more complicated things are the lower the proportion. Regardless of the issue's simple or challenging, the difficulty index is interpreted using the majority criteria (50% plus 1). The item is neither easy nor challenging if its difficulty index is 50%; the lower the proportion, the more complicated it is. Lastly, the researcher determined the discriminating power of the item in step 6. The correct responses were compared to the higher and lower groups to assess the item's discriminating potential. The index of discrimination was computed using the formula below:

$$\text{Index of discrimination} = \frac{RU - RL}{NG}$$

To discuss the formula, RU presents the proper response of the upper group, while RL is the appropriate response of the lower group, and NG is the member of each group's learners.

According to Hartati and Yogi (2019), the discriminating power of an item is not more than 1.00. A maximum of positive discriminator power is revealed by an index of 1.00. It is obtained when all upper-group learners choose the correct answer, not the lower group. When more students in the lower group than the higher group receive the correct answers, this is known as negative discriminating power. Furthermore, when the correct response is given to the upper and lower groups with equal frequency, a zero-discriminating power (0.00) is reached. The components with zero and negative discriminating power must be enhanced or changed. Table 2 presents the discrimination index and the difficulty of the test item.

Table 1. *The Index of Discrimination and Difficulty of Test Item*

<i>Index Of Discrimination</i>	<i>Item Evaluation</i>
0.40 or higher	Very Good Item
0.30 – 0.39	Good Item
0.20 – 0.29	Marginal Item
0.19 or below	Poor Item
<i>Index Of Difficulty</i>	<i>Item Evaluation</i>
0.70 or higher	Low Difficulty
0.31 – 0.69	Moderate Difficulty
0.30 or below	High Difficulty

The proponent kept the items that passed the item analysis's discrimination index and complexity tests. Additional items that were noted as improved or updated were completed. The tests with sixty items were face-validated. Three (3) master professors who are specialists in the field validated it. The following standards were used to validate the instrument: congruency with the purpose, the impartiality of the researcher, appropriateness of the options and evaluation rating system, appropriateness of the items, appropriateness of the indicators per category, presentation, and organization, and clarity of direction and indicators. They contributed their skills to the changes and enhancements.

Out of the 60-item Test in Mathematics 3 that underwent the validation and piloting process, the researcher created an official 30-item Test used in the pretest-test and post-test activities. The items came from the supplementary materials.

Procedure

The researcher conducted experimental research using a single-group design by Nugraha (2021). The construction of the auxiliary materials came initially. In Mathematics, the researcher created supplemental resources for the second quarter. There were four modules in it. The second step involved the validation of the modules by the District, Division, and Division ICT coordinators' expert validators. They scrutinized the modules and adhered to the validation procedures. Pilot testing was the third step. The researcher used Kuder Richarson's Formula to administer the test to the study subjects to ascertain whether the items were legitimate. The fourth step was the item analysis. Item analysis allows the researcher to determine which item to retain, revise, improve, or remove. The fifth step was the final questionnaires for the pretest-test and post-test. The researcher finalized the questionnaire to be conducted among 35 Grade 3 learners. After finalizing the questionnaire, the researcher conducted the pre-test test on the study subjects. The next step is to experiment for five months. The next step was to conduct a post-test after the experiment. In the last step, the results will be analyzed by comparing the pre-test, pre-test, and post-test to determine the effectiveness of the teacher-made digital games in teaching Mathematics 3.

Table 2. *Cronbach's Alpha Internal Consistency*

<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Internal Consistency</i>
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$	Good
$0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$	Acceptable
$0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$	Questionable
$0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$	Poor
$0.5 > \alpha$	Unacceptable

It administered the re-test method of the instrument to Maitum Elementary School, Division of Sarangani.

Table 3. *Reliability Statistics*

<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items</i>	<i>Number of Items</i>
.901	.8839	30

The results showed that Cronbach's alpha was excellent for internal consistency: $\alpha = .901$. The researcher can trust the instrument.

Ethical Considerations

For this quantitative study, a critical ethical factor has specific ramifications. These problems and worries can primarily result from the approach used in this study. The ethical considerations in this research were concerned with the proper conduct of the study, confidentiality, and anonymity. The RMMC Ethics and Review Committee's requirements for ethical consideration were adhered to in this study, especially when it came to the population and data, including but not limited to:

Voluntary Participation. The respondents were free to participate without fear of consequences, loss of benefits, or compensation plans. Therefore, after discussing the study's purpose and benefits, the subject's rights to provide the body of knowledge were carefully measured and foresighted. The respondents in this study were coerced into taking part. If people got uncomfortable while participating in the study, they were allowed to stop.

Privacy and confidentiality. According to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which upholds the fundamental human right to privacy, respondents have a right to privacy that cannot be infringed upon without the respondents' informed agreement. Allowing respondents to omit their names from the survey questionnaire is one technique to maintain privacy and confidentiality in this quantitative study. Additionally, secrecy and privacy were achieved by withholding the informants' demographic information, such as age, gender, occupation, and medical condition. As a result, their identity was kept private for security reasons. Their answers to the survey questionnaire were kept private and treated as such.

Informed consent process. The prospective research respondents were fully informed about the research's objectives, methods, and benefits as comprehensively as possible within the framework of the study. The respondents' written consent was obtained, indicating their participation was asked voluntarily. The respondents signed the informed consent form stating they willingly consented to participate in the study. Since the respondents were learners, asking for parents' consent was necessary. The respondents' identities were not mentioned on the survey form, and their responses were kept private. The participants knew they could withdraw from participating in the study anytime.

Furthermore, any data the researcher gathered was protected, and releasing any information would follow a strict informed consent process. The respondents would control their personal information to lessen their fear that the data or information would be used in any other unintended manner.

Recruitment. The respondents were informed of why they had become part of the study. The researcher explained the study's goal to the respondents to facilitate further inference and comprehension of its fundamentals. In addition to the letter, the researcher explained

the purpose of the study and its importance.

Risks. The research was conducted to determine an acceptable positive benefit-risk ratio. This study's need to protect the respondents from significant harm was equally essential. Therefore, the study prioritized the welfare of the respondents. Furthermore, the subjects were not harmed since their identity was held confidential. Their security and safety were of the utmost concern. The researcher needed to ensure that the subjects were physically, emotionally, and socially ready. In answering the survey questionnaire, the researcher confirmed that subjects did not feel discomfort or awkwardness.

Benefits. The global significance of using digital games in teaching mathematics is their ability to make math education more accessible and engaging across geographical and cultural boundaries. These games offer interactive learning experiences, enabling students to explore math concepts, practice problem-solving, and receive immediate feedback. The research aims to benefit education by improving teaching devices and numeracy skills, potentially impacting the Department of Education, School Division Superintendents, and school leaders. It may serve as a baseline for enhancing academic performance in math through localized teacher-made digital games and promote localized activities and computational thinking skill development. Additionally, it may provide technical assistance and benefit parents and the community.

Plagiarism. The study has no trace or evidence of misinterpretation of someone else's work. It was subjected to plagiarism detectors like Grammarly software. Cheerful character and integrity, linked to moral characteristics and ideals, are essential for researchers. In order to produce a trustworthy research report, the researcher also has to have a deeper understanding of the plagiarism paradigm.

Fabrication. The paper does not hint or suggest that the work was intentionally misinterpreted. There was no fabrication of information or outcomes or deliberate presentation of incorrect conclusions. Instead, the investigator utilized and incorporated ideas associated with the data and additional inferential notions.

Falsification. The study did not purposefully misrepresent the work to fit a model or theoretical expectation and had no evidence of overclaiming or exaggeration. Furthermore, the data for this study had to be manipulated, which required crafting claims, omitting crucial information, and using supplies, equipment, or procedures that may deceive others.

Conflict of Interest (COI). The study has no trace of conflicts of interest, such as the disclosure of COI, which is a collection of circumstances under which professional judgment regarding primary claims like subjects' welfare or the validity of the research tends to be influenced by a secondary interest such as financial or academic gains or recognitions. Furthermore, the researcher had no control or influence over the subjects, forcing them to be part of the study.

Deceit. There was no evidence that the study misled the subjects about potential risks. The rights of everybody who participated in an investigation were fiercely protected, especially if they had completed higher education. Therefore, reasonable and suitable standards were followed.

Permission from Organization/Location. The researcher of this study followed protocols. Upon receiving the signal from the panelists, adviser, and committee of the RMMCERC, the researcher sought approval from the school's division superintendent to conduct the study through a formal letter. Following this, the researcher composed an official letter and attached the school's division superintendent's endorsed letter to the district supervisor and principal of the participating schools in the study. The learners who participated in the study were oriented before administering the survey questionnaire.

Authorship. Ethical authorship ensures that all individuals who contributed substantially to the research were appropriately acknowledged as authors. In contrast, those who did not meet the criteria for authorship were not included. The researcher ensured that the study's results appropriately reflected the contributions of all parties involved and were fair and transparent. Research outputs maintained their credibility and made a fair and transparent contribution to the progress of knowledge by abiding by ethical authoring norms.

Results

This section presents results, analyzes them, and interprets the data gathered on the pre-test and post-test scores and the significant relationship between learners' pre-test and post-test scores.

3.1. The Pre-test Mean Scores of the Subjects

Table 3 presented the pretest-test mean scores of Grade 3 learners in Mathematics before using teacher-made digital games. It utilized using the frequency counts and percentage distribution of the learners' scores in the pre-test test.

The data showed that most learners obtained a low pretest-test score. Out of 35 learners, 23 learners garnered low pre-test scores, 8 obtained moderately high pre-test scores, 3 got high pre-test scores, only one learner obtained a very high pre-test score, and no learner obtained a meager pre-test score.

This result implied that the majority of the thirty-five learners had a low level of knowledge or understanding in the subject area being assessed, as indicated by their low pre-test scores. It showed that to help them comprehend and perform better in that particular area,

there could be a need for focused remedial or instructional interventions. Additionally, it was notable that none of the learners obtained shallow pretest-test scores, which could indicate a baseline level of familiarity with the subject matter. However, still, efforts should be made to elevate their performance.

3.2. The Post-Test Mean Scores of the Subjects

Table 4 presented the post-test mean scores of the Grade 3 learners in Mathematics after using teacher-made digital games. The collected data was handled using percentage distributions and frequency counts.

The table showed that most learners obtained a high post-test score. Out of 35 learners, 17 obtained high post-test scores, 14 got moderately high post-test scores, 4 garnered very high post-test scores, and no learner obtained low post-test scores. The result implied that there was an increase in the post-test scores after the utilization of teacher-made digital games.

The results implied that using teacher-made digital games positively impacted the learners' performance. Most of the 35 learners achieved high or very high post-test scores, indicating a substantial improvement in their understanding and knowledge after engaging with the digital games. Notably, none of the learners scored low or very low on the post-test, suggesting that using these games effectively enhanced their learning outcomes. It drew attention to the possibility of teacher-created digital games as a valuable teaching aid for raising student achievement. It underscored the value of incorporating interactive and engaging methods into teaching practices.

Table 4. *The Post-Test Mean Scores of the Subjects*

Description	Frequency	Percentage
Very High (25-30)	4	11
High (19-24)	17	49
Moderately High (13-18)	14	40
Low (7-12)	0	0
Very Low	0	0

3.3. Significant Difference between Pre-test and Post-Test Mean Scores of Grade 3 Learners in Mathematics

Table 5 presented the significant difference between the pretest-test and post-test mean scores of Grade 3 learners in Mathematics.

Data revealed that when the pretest-test and post-test scores of learners were tested at the Alpha level of .05 with a df of 33, the computed value was 10.56. It was more significant than the tabular value of 1.697, which led to rejecting the null hypothesis. Therefore, using teacher-made digital games in Mathematics positively impacted the Grade 3 learners.

Table 5. *Significant Difference Between Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores of Grades 3 Learners in Mathematics*

Score	Df n-2	U-Value		Decision	Analysis
		Computed	Tabular		
Pre-test Vs Post-Test	33	10.56	1.697	Reject Null Hypothesis	Significant

The implication between the pretest-test and post-test scores of the learners is that the utilization of teacher-made digital games had a notably positive effect on their learning outcomes. Most students showed a significant improvement from their pre-test and post-test scores, with a substantial number achieving high and very high post-test scores. It indicates that the digital games effectively facilitated learning and comprehension, helping students progress and demonstrating the potential of interactive, technology-enhanced teaching methods. Additionally, the absence of low post-test scores suggests that the digital games effectively addressed gaps in understanding, resulting in overall enhanced performance among the learners.

Discussion

This section discusses the data on using teacher-made digital games in teaching mathematics to Grade 3 learners.

Pre-test Mean Scores of Grades 3 Learners in Mathematics

Most Grade 3 learners had low scores during the pre-test test. It indicates that learners must still acquire the necessary knowledge or skills for a particular task or subject area. This assumption parallels the study of Hossein-Mohand et al. (2021), who claim that if an individual scores low on a pretest-test, it means that they may struggle with the material covered in the course or program and may require additional support and resources to catch up and improve their understanding. However, low pretest-test scores do not necessarily mean an individual can fail the course or program. With effort and appropriate support, one can improve one's knowledge and skills and perform well in the course or program.

The study conducted by Hillmayr et al., (2020) stated that digital games offer various options for teaching mathematics, including math adventure games and math racing games. Math adventure games create immersive experiences where students solve puzzles and navigate through virtual worlds, integrating math concepts into an exciting narrative. On the other hand, math racing games provide opportunities for students to practice and enhance their math skills by solving problems quickly and accurately, competing against

virtual opponents. By incorporating these digital games into mathematics education, students can engage in enjoyable and compelling learning experiences that promote acquiring and applying math concepts and skills.

According to Bakan and Bakan (2018), educators should be consistent with children's interests and integrate modern teaching methods into the education system, motivating students more than ordinary classroom instruction. Video and digital games are also convenient in enhancing students' motivation and learning progress, as they enrich their experiences.

Post-Test Mean Scores of Grades 3 Learners in Mathematics

Most Grade 3 learners obtained high post-test scores after using teacher-made digital games. There was a significant increase in the post-test scores of learners compared to their pre-test scores. It indicates that learners have acquired significant knowledge or skills in a particular subject area or task after completing a course or program. This assumption parallels the study of Bertram (2020), who claims that post-tests are usually administered after the completion of a course or program to measure the extent to which the participants have learned and retained the material covered.

Suppose an individual scores high on a post-test. In that case, they have demonstrated a good understanding of the material covered in the course or program and have developed the necessary knowledge and skills to perform well in the subject area. High post-test scores indicate that the individual has worked hard, put in the necessary effort and dedication, and received adequate support and resources during the course or program. Overall, high post-test scores are usually a positive indication that an individual has successfully achieved the learning objectives of the course or program and is well-equipped to apply their knowledge and skills in real-world situations.

Based on the study of Soboleva et al. (2021), new teaching methods in mathematics education prioritize hands-on activities, collaborative problem-solving, and real-world applications to foster student exploration and discovery of mathematical concepts. These methods aim to develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and communication skills alongside mathematical knowledge. Furthermore, technology, including digital games, virtual manipulatives, and online resources, has expanded math teaching and learning opportunities. Students may work independently and get immediate feedback on their progress thanks to these technologies, which provide personalized and adaptable learning experiences.

The Use of Teacher-Made Digital Games in Teaching Mathematics 3

Data revealed a significant difference in the pretest-test and post-test scores of Grade 3 learners. It indicates that using teacher-made digital games was effective in teaching Mathematics 3. The result is supported by the Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning by Mayer (2019), which asserts that deeper learning is achieved when information is presented using a combination of text and graphics as opposed to text alone. This theory draws from cognitive science principles and emphasizes the role of educational technology in enhancing effective learning. Educators can promote better comprehension, memory retention, and the practical application of knowledge by utilizing a presentation format that incorporates both textual and visual elements. In essence, this approach creates more impactful and compelling learning experiences for students by capitalizing on the cognitive benefits of multimedia learning.

Conclusion

Based on the study's results, the following conclusions were formulated and established: First, most of the learners obtained a low pretest-test score before using teacher-made digital games. Second, most of the learners obtained a high post-test score after using teacher-made digital games. Lastly, there was a significant difference in the pretest-test and post-test scores of the learners. Nevertheless, using teacher-made digital games effectively improved learners' academic performance in Mathematics 3. Despite the challenges, using teacher-made digital games have proven to be an effective tool in enhancing the academic performance of Mathematics 3 learners.

The following recommendations were established based on the conclusions of the study: Globally, the use of digital games in teaching mathematics can transcend geographical and cultural boundaries, making mathematics education more accessible, engaging, and inclusive for learners worldwide. Additionally, engaging and immersive learning experiences can be facilitated via digital games, allowing students to practice problem-solving techniques, explore mathematical ideas, and get quick feedback. Further, the information gathered in this research may benefit education. It could serve as a basis for improving the teaching devices in the public education setting with teachers' engagement. The results may improve the numeracy skills of learners.

Similarly, the results of this study may bring added literature and data to the Department of Education (DepEd). Schools Division Superintendents may use the study's results as baseline data for crafting additional programs and activities to strengthen the learners' academic performance. It may also add a milestone in improving teaching Mathematics by providing localized and contextualized teacher-made digital math games that may eventually improve learners' academic performance in Mathematics. Moreover, this study may allow school leaders to conduct localized activities.

Teachers may also give them essential opportunities to develop programs and projects to locally enhance learners' computational thinking skills. Technical assistance may also be provided after the consolidation of this study. This study may also benefit the parents and community.

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